

Students' Academic Dishonesty In Midwifery Department

Rani Autila^{1✉},

rani.autila.academic@gmail.com¹

¹Jurusan Ilmu Keperawatan, Sekolah Tinggi Ilmu Kesehatan, Indonesia

Keywords: Academic, Dishonesty, English, Examination	Abstract
Submitted: 25/12/2025	<p>This research was conducted to describe students' academic dishonesty in examination process at Midwifery Department of Sekolah Tinggi Ilmu Kesehatan Indonesia. This study used the theory from Miller et al (2017) students' academic dishonesty is a fraudulent or unfair act to produce better results on exams, papers, assignments, and other learning assignments. The researcher used a qualitative approach with descriptive research. Techniques in data collection is questionnaires. Research result show that the forms of academic dishonesty that students sometimes do are copy friends' answer during exam, allow friends to copy answer sheet during the test, collaborate with friends during the test, use handphone to find answer during exam, use signal/finger code to friend to get answer. The result of students' academic dishonesty is sometimes 15 %.</p>
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<p>Author Correspondent: Rani Autila Jurusan Ilmu Keperawatan, Sekolah Tinggi Ilmu Kesehatan, Indonesia Jln. Khatib Sulaiman No 17 rani.autila.academic@gmail.com</p>	

INTRODUCTION

Examination is aiming to measure students' ability, knowledge, and learning outcomes. Examination or test to give collect the information about students' achievement during a learning process. Test will help the students to improve their ability in comprehending a specific subject, by following a test the students will know that they are comprehending enough about the material or not. The result of a test will show about the students' achievement, and it will be a data for the teacher about which students that should give an extra attention.

The challenge faced by education is academic dishonesty. This academic dishonesty is frequently in schools and done by students when doing assignments or examination. This fraudulent act occurs because students want to get academic success by using illegitimate means. It is supported by Sariasih & Tisnawijaya (2019) the students will do anything; study hard, focus on their assignment and project, and prepared themselves before the exam. However, not all students have the same way in order to

get a high score, they tend to have a shortcut and perform academic dishonesty. The teacher must pay attention about academic dishonesty that may disturb the process of the exams and assignment in order to make accurate result. For this reason, teacher must know how students do academic dishonesty in English examination process.

RESEARCH METHODS

This study used qualitative approach with descriptive research. Descriptive research as research design that described the phenomenon that happened in the field. The sample used in this study was 13 students of Midwifery Department in 2025 academic year of Sekolah Tinggi Ilmu Kesehatan Indonesia. The sampling technique used was total sampling. In this research, the instrument is a questionnaire to collect the data about forms of students' academic dishonesty in the examination process. Data collection was carried out by distributing questionnaires about forms of academic cheating that are often carried out during exams. It was composed by using Rating Scale. Rating scaling is commonly used tool measuring a respondent's attitudes toward self, others, activities, institutions, or situations. Therefore, the present scale comprised 5-point rating format, each statement is rated on five sequential point, (always=1, frequently=2, sometimes=3, rarely=4 and never=5).

In gathering the data in the field for analyzing the students' academic dishonesty, the researcher did some steps. First, the researcher prepared questionnaire. Second, the researcher came to classroom to share questionnaire sheet to students. Third, the researcher analyzed it by applying techniques of data analysis, the researcher analyzed the data based on the instrumentation. According to Gay L. R., Geoffrey E. Mills (2012), there are four steps to analyze the data. They are reading/memoing, describing, classifying and interpreting.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Student Use Crib Note on a Test

The first item was categorized as never with a percentage 84%. There were 8% students who choose rarely. Then 8% student answer sometimes. In addition, there are no students chose often and always. It means the students were not interested to use crib note on a test.

Table Presentation

Table 1. Use crib note on a test

Sub indicator	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Always
I use crib note on a test	11	1	1	0	0

Figure 1. Use crib note on a test

The Student Copies the Answer from Another Student

The second item was categorized never with a percentage 54%. There are 15% students who chose rarely. Then 31% students answered sometimes. This shows that

students sometimes copy friends' answers during exam. In addition, there are no students chose often and always.

Table 2. Copy friends' answer during exam

Sub indicator	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Always
I copy friends answer during exam	7	2	4	0	0

Figure 2. Copy friends' answer during example

The Student Copies from Another Student During A Test Without His or Her Permission

The third item was categorized as never with a percentage 85%. There are 15% students who chose rarely. Then, no students answered sometimes, often, and always. This shows that students rarely copy from another student during a test without his or her permission.

Table 3. Copy from another student during a test without his or her permission

Sub indicator	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Always
I copy from another student during a test without his or her permission.	0	26	7	5	2

Figure 3. Copy from another student during a test without his or her permission.

The Students Allow Their Friends to Copy Their Answer Sheet During the Test

The fourth item was categorized rarely with a percentage 38%. There are 31% students who chose never, because students know that during the exam must not give each other answers. Then 23% students answered sometimes. In addition, there are 8% students who chose often and 0 % students choose always. This is because students do not have preparation in the test process.

Table 4. Allow my friend to copy my answer sheet during the test

Sub indicator	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Always
I allow my friend to copy my answer sheet during the test	4	5	3	1	0

Figure 4. Allow my friend to copy my answer sheet during the test

There Is an Authorized Collaboration During the Test

The fifth item was categorized as sometimes with a percentage of 38%. There are 31% students who chose never, because students know that during the exam cannot discuss. Then, 31% students answered rarely. In addition, there are no students who chose often and always.

Table 5. Collaborate with my friend during the test

Sub indicator	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Always
I collaborate with my friend during the test	4	4	5	0	0

Figure 5. Collaborate with my friend during the test

The Student Gets the Answer from The Other Class Already Taken Exam

The sixth item was categorized as never with a percentage 54%. There are 46% students who chose rarely, because students master the subject matter to be examined. Then, no students answered sometimes, often, and always.

Table 6. Get the answer from the other class already taken exam

Sub indicator	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Always
I get the answer from the other class already taken exam	7	6	0	0	0

Figure 6. Get the answer from the other class already taken exam

The student cheat in any other way during test

The seventh item was categorized as never with a percentage 69%. Students do not use technology to find answers because students master the subject matter examined. There are 23% students who chose sometimes because they were looking for answers with Google. Then 8% students answer rarely. In addition, no one choose often and always.

Table 7. The students cheat in any other way during test

Sub indicator	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Always
I use handphone to find answer during exam	9	1	3	0	0

Figure 7. The students cheat in any other way during test

The students use signal/finger code to friend to get answer

Eighth item was categorized as rarely with percentage of 61% because students quite master the exam material. There are 23% students who choose sometimes, because students do not master the subject matter to be examined. Then 8 % students answered always and never. In addition, no students chose often.

Table 8. The students use signal/finger code to friend to get answer

Sub indicator	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Always
I use signal/finger code to friend to get answer	1	8	3	0	1

Figure 8. The students use signal/finger code to friend to get answer

The students open book to find answer during exam

Ninth item was categorized as never with a percentage of 69%. Students never open books secretly to find answers during the exam. Then 31% students answer rarely. In addition, no students chose sometimes, often and always.

Table 9. The students open book to find answer during exam

Sub indicator	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Always
I open book to find answer during exam	9	4	0	0	0

Figure 9. The students open book to find answer during exam

Table 10. The student receives and ask friends to help during the exam

Sub indicator	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Always
I Receive And Ask Friend To Help During The Exam	8	4	1	0	0

Figure 10. The student receives and ask friends to help during the exam

The form of dishonest behavior that arises are asking for answers from friends, cheating friends, and expecting friends' help. In accordance with the opinion from Nursalam, Bani, and Munirah (2013) imitating the work of friends, asking friends directly when working on tests, doing assignments with friends are categorized as cheating.

Table 11. Students' academic dishonesty in examination process

Category	Frequency	Percentage
Never	71	55%
Rarely	37	28%
Sometimes	20	15%
Often	1	1%
Always	1	1%
Amount	130	100%

Figure 11. Students' academic dishonesty in examination process

Based on the results of research above, the students' dishonesty is in never category, this is evidenced by the results of the percentage of students at 55% of

students committing honesty during the exam process. Forms of honest and dishonest behavior when taking exams are revealed in 3 situations, namely a) when students face exams on two subjects in a day while only one subject has been studied, b) when students see their friends' cheating each other, c) when students have not finished studying then made small notes to answer the questions.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Conclusion

The researcher did the research to get the data about students' academic dishonesty in examination process. Based on the results of the research described, there were forms of academic dishonesty carried out by students, namely, copying answer, seeing friends' answer without their permission, collaborating, using handphone, asking help to friend, using crib notes, opening book, solving answer with signal/finger code and etcetera. The following conclusions can be put forward: students' academic dishonesty in the examination process in the sometimes category with a result of 15%.

The first highest indicators percentage is 38% for students collaborate with friends during the test. The second highest indicators percentage is 31% for copying friends' answer during exam. The third indicators percentage is 23% for student use signal/finger code to friend to get answer, cheat in any other way during test and allow friends to copy answer sheet during the test.

Suggestion

After conducting the study and receiving the results, the researcher wanted to make a suggestion that the students should be more honest during examination. Honestly is really important rather than dishonest to get high grade. It is a character building; university as educational institution must emphasize the important of honest in examination and teaching learning process. So, the students can implement it in their real life. For further researcher, it is recommended to study about students' honest in doing assignment that given by teacher.

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